

Supplementary Figure 1. Volcano plot of differentially expressed genes ($\text{padj} < 0.01$, $\text{LFC} > 1$).

Supplementary Figure 2. Outlier detected by sample clustering (WGCNA).

Supplementary Figure 3. Principal component analysis of herd effect. A) with herd effect, B) herd effect removed

